

D1.1 – Data Management Plan

prepared for

WP1 – Project Management

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Approved by: Paul Zabel

DLR

Project Leader

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
1	DLR	P. Zabel
2	LSG	
3	TUBS	
4	SW	
5	PWR	
6	TAS	

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Executive summary

Sustainable space exploration requires the development of In-Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU) technologies, which encompass all processes that utilize local resources to generate useful products for robotic and human exploration. Among the available resources, water is the most versatile and most needed in space exploration. Water can be directly used as consumable for astronauts or electrolyzed to hydrogen and oxygen, a very effective rocket propellant combination. However, in-situ water extraction is challenging and the required technologies are not yet fully developed. The proposed LUXEX project foresees the development and validation of a complete in-situ water process chain including water extraction, purification and quality monitoring. An integrated test setup will be built to validate the operational capabilities of these technologies and also of the whole process chain. This setup will deliver a relatively realistic environment analogue to the lunar surface and will use a lunar dust-ice simulant to provide proper validation conditions to raise the TRL of all subsystems and the whole process chain to level 4.

This data management plan (DMP) is describing how the project consortium deals with the data generated during the project. The document is updated throughout the project at critical milestones. Version number and change log can be found on pages 1 and 2.

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1 Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

The research conducted in this project does not rely on existing data.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

Generated data will consist of process and experiment parameters such as, e.g.: temperature, pressure, flowrate, water quality.

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The main purpose of the data is the validation of the subsystems developed and tested in this project. A secondary purpose is the refining of simulation models representing the physical processes occurring inside the subsystems.

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

At the current stage of the project, the size of the data is difficult to assess, but the project consortiums estimate that the data will be in the order of a few GB.

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The data primarily originates from the experiment campaign, which is planned for the last quarter of the project.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data generated in this project can be useful for planetary scientist, space engineers and moon mission planners and be used for the design of future systems and for simulation and modelling of physical processes.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes, a persistent identifier in the form of a DOI will be created for each dataset when uploaded to the project's repository on zenodo.org and complemented with keywords.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The metadata that will be created is: Project name, publishing date, author and co-author names, the institution(s) that the author(s) are working from, name, version, language and page number for the article within a journal if the paper has been published.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes, keywords will be provided.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes, the data will be provided.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Yes, the datasets will be provided through the project's repository on zenodo.org.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Different options were investigated, but the project coordinator DLR already has experience with the selected repository which led to the decision.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Yes, the repository allows the generation and assignment of identifiers to datasets.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Most experimental data will be made openly available after giving the consortium partners the chance to use the data for publications or patent applications.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

The project partners will follow a typical embargo period of six months for data that is used for publications.

If data is used for filing patents, the embargo period will last until the patent application was filed in with the patent office of the partner's country of origin.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

Yes, data will be made accessible as described as much as is possible.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

No restriction on the use of the data exists, apart from giving the appropriate credit to the data creator.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

The identity of the person accessing the data is not ascertained.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee.

Metadata:**Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**

Metadata is openly available and contains enough information (direct link) to enable the user to access the data.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Both data and metadata stored in the zenodo.org repository will remain available indefinitely.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

If necessary, the required software to access the data will be mentioned in the information provided to each dataset.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

No special vocabulary is used in the project.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

Not applicable.

Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Not applicable.

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

All datasets published in the zenodo.org repository must have comprehensive documentation addressing the data structure, the definition of variables, and the units of measurement. Ideally, the documentation is published in peer-review journals.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All datasets published in the zenodo.org repository are made freely available and licensed under the Creative Commons 4.0 CC-BY-NC license.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

All datasets published in the zenodo.org repository are freely usable by anyone.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The documentation and metadata of each dataset recognize the data provenance through proper citation of the source of information using the formats usually accepted by the relevant scientific community.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Each consortium partner will follow their respective quality assurance processes.

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

This is addressed in the following subsections.

3 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

When other research outputs are generated, the management of those outputs will be discussed with all consortium partners. At the current stage of the project this cannot be answered yet.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

When other research outputs are generated, compliance with the FAIR principles shall be managed by their creators.

4 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

At the current stage of the project, we do not see there being any extra costs incurred.

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).

Currently inapplicable.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data management is under the responsibility of DLR, who is the coordinator of the project.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

This question cannot be answered at the current stage of the project.

5 Data Security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Experiment data is backed up locally on multiple hard drives of the experiment PCs and also transferred into cloud storage space of the consortium partners every day during the experiment campaign. This allows the recovery of data in case of hardware or software failures. By the end of the experiment campaign the data is stored in repositories which include automatic back-ups.

No sensitive data is collected or stored.

6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

The project consortium sees no ethical or legal reasons that could have an impact on data sharing.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No questionnaires or collection of personal data is foreseen in this project.